

Variation of Seed and Seedlings Characteristics of *Moringa Oleifera* from Different Seed Provenances in Sudan

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Abstract

Success in growth and yield of forest tree is determined basically by seed sources. So provenances variation in seed and seedling g attributes of *Moringa oleifera* adaptability experiment was conducted at the nursery. The objective of the study was to assess the growth performance and adaptation of *Moringa oleifera* to the central Sudan area depending on their early growth patterns and survival. The seeds from four provenances were sown and compared using randomized complete block design with four replications. It showed that there was a significant difference in height growth ($p=0.0001$), diameter at root collar ($p=0.001$), and leaf number ($p=0.001$) measured in the 3rd month of germination. This could be due to the environmental factors and inherent genetic potentials of the species which generally govern tree growth. The Eastern provenances seem to be superior over other in the studied characters (height growth, diameter at root collar and leaf number). These three variables are crucial for survival in arid and semi-arid conditions as the seedlings were sturdier and the root system can penetrate longer deep in the soil for moisture even in the drier season. The study recommended that the comprehensive provenances treatments are indispensable to facilitate drawing more results on its adaptive.

Keywords: Diameter, root collar, germination, leaves number, weight.

Introduction

Moringa oleifera La is native from India, occurring wild in the sub-Himalayan regions of Northern India, and now it is distributed in many countries of the tropics and subtropics. (Demeulenaere 2001; Melesse et al. 2011). Commonly known as the 'horse-radish' tree (arising from the taste of a condiment prepared from the roots) or 'drumstick' tree (arising from the shape of the pods), While in the Sudan, the name of the tree is (rawag -shagar alrawag- kelor- akseer alhiaa).(El Amin 1973; Jahn 1976; Anwar et al.,2003 ; Hussein Y ,2009).According to Andrews (1950) *Moringa oleifera* was introduced from India but in the area of KafiyaKingi in southern Darfur it occurs as an indigenous tree. *Moringa oleifera* called multipurpose tree because its pods, seeds, leaves and roots are useful as fodder, vegetable and plant growth enhancer (Khantharajah et al.,1991 ; Veeraragava 1998 ; Mughal et al., 1999; Anhwange et al., 2004, Sanchez et al., 2006; Nouman et al., 2012a) Besides being consumed by humans, (Bennett et al.,2003 ; Gidamis et al.,2003). It is also used as animal fodder (Sanchez et al.,2006 ;Nouman et al.,2012 b., Suarez et al.,2003) , used as natural coagulant of turbid water and source of phytomedical compounds (Anwar et al., 2006). *Moringa oleifera* widely cultivated especially in dry tropical areas of Middle East and Africa (Fahey2005 ; Palada et al., 2007;Nouman et al.,2012a)but information available on cultivation procedures is limited, except in certain regions of India where it is cultivated on a

large scale (Bezerra et al., 2004). Since conclusive information on morphological variation in seed characteristics and seedling of a species amongst the provenances has been reported to be useful for tree improvement programs (Singh et al. 2010) Provenance testing of a tree species is important because it defines the genetic and environmental components of phenotypic variations that are associated with geographic locations (Callaham 1964; Zobel and Talbert 1984). It will also help in providing planting materials for forestry and to encourage increased cultivation and domestication of the species and its integration into agrarian system. Selection of the best provenance of a species for a given site or region is necessary to achieve maximum productivity in agro-forestry. This study aimed to obtain the most suitable provenances (from different regions in Sudan) for the production of high quality seedlings (planting materials) for mass afforestation in agro-forestry systems and to evaluate the variation existing in different provenances of *Moringa oleifera* based on seed weight, germination and early seedling growth.

Materials and Methods

Seed sources

Seed materials used in the study collected from four provenances. Elfasher (13° 37' 50"N, 25° 21' E annual rainfall 186.7 mm, altitude 700 m, maximum temperature 34.1 °C and temperature 16 °C) labeled as Western provenances, White Nile (Ad Diwem 14° 0' 4N 32° 18' 42E, annual rainfall 274 mm, altitude 376m, maximum temperature 41.2 °C and min temp 16.3°C) labeled as Central provenance and Gedaref (14 ° 2' N 35 ° 23' E annual rainfall 750 mm, Altitude 580m, *Moringa oleifera* maximum temperature 47 °C and minimum temperature 17 °C) labeled as Eastern provenance; Dongola (19° 10' N 30° 29' E annual rainfall 17.6 mm altitude 226m, maximum temperature 43°C and minimum temperature 17.6 °C) labeled as Northern provenance with the help of the National Tree Seed Center of the Forestry Research Centre, Agricultural research Corporation.

Seed weight

For each provenance eight replicates of 100 seed were weighed separately using sensitive electronic balance, weights were recorded up to two decimal places. The mean was calculated and then the difference between weights was evaluated. (Jovoll and Mahgoub, 1994). The number of seeds per kilogram was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Number of seeds per kilogram} = \frac{100 \times 1000 \text{ g}}{A}$$

Where; A is the weight of 100 seeds (g)

Next, an experiment was conducted to assess Provenance variation of *Moringa* at early stage of growth. The experiment took place in the nursery of the Forests National Corporation at Ad Diwem, White Nile state, following the regular nursery practice for raising forest tree seedlings. The seedlings grow in polythene bags of 25 cm width by 30 cm length. The soil used was river silt, no fertilizers were used and three seeds were grow in each bag. The seedlings were watered every three days through flood irrigation which is the common practice with sunken nursery bed. The seedlings were placed in beds under the partial shade; using a completed randomized block design with 4 replicates. For each provenance, 240

seedlings were raised i.e. 60 seedlings per plot. The germination parameters were calculated as follows

1) Seed germination percentage was calculated using the following formula [ISTA1999]:

Germination percentage = Number of germinated seeds / Total number of seeds × 100

2) Germination associate parameters were calculated by using following formulas:

a) Speed of germination

Speed of germination was calculated by the following formula given by [Czabator1962].

Speed of germination = $n_1/d_1 + n_2/d_2 + n_3/d_3 + \dots$ / Where, n = number of germinated seeds, d = number of days.

b) Mean germination Time (MGT)

Mean germination time was calculated by the formula given by [Ellis and Roberts1981]

MGT = $n_1 \times d_1 + n_2 \times d_2 + n_3 \times d_3 + \dots$ / Total number of days

Where, n = number of germinated seed

d = number of days

c) Mean daily germination (MDG)

Mean daily germination can be calculated by the following formula given by [Czabator1962]

MDG = Total number of germinated seeds / Total number of days

d) Value (PV)Peak

Peak value was calculated by the following formula given by [Czabator1962].

PV = Highest seed germinated / Number of days

e) Germination Value (GV): Germination value was calculated by the following formula given by [Czabator1962]. $GV = PV \times MDG$

Then the seedlings were dried at 80°C until a constant weight was obtained and the following assessments made: Total dry weight (g) shoot dry weight (g) and root dry weight (g).

Data analysis: Statistical analysis was performed by the JMP package (Programme improved from SAS Package) (SAS Institute Inc. 1989); the means were compared using a Tukey Kramer test.

Results and Disection

Table 1 Germination parameters of *Moringa oleifera* seed grown in four provenances

Provinces	Location	Number of seeds kg ⁻¹	GP	SG	MGT	MDG	PV	GV
Eastern	Gedaref	3401	100	25.6	23.7	1	1.9	1.9
Northern	Dongola	3968	88	25.0	24.9	.88	1.5	1.32
Central	Ad Diwem	3333	83.7	22.3	27.3	.83	1.4	1.16
Western	Elfasher	4385	78.1	22.6	32.4	.78	1.34	1.05

GP: Germination percentage, SG: Speed of germination, MGT: Mean germination Time (MGT), MDG: Mean daily germination, PV: Value Peak (PV), GV: Germination value

The results in table (1) showed significant differences between four provenances on seeds per kilogram and germination parameter. The North provenance (Dongola) ranking at the top with highest seed number, while the lowest number of seeds was recorded by provenance (Gedaref). The provenances showed no similarity with each other in this characteristic as the seed weight ranged from (3333 to 4385). Germination was affected by regional differences. Seeds from Gedaref which were physically the largest in weight had the

highest germination percentage (100%). The results showed higher growth speeds of larger seed than smaller seeds. Similar results have been reported for other tropical tree species (Marshall, 1986; Murali, 1997; Khan et al. 1999). Further, the positive correlation of seedling vigour with initial seed weight suggests that seedlings from heavy weight seeds are more competitive. This finding agrees with Fandohan et al.(2010) and Bonfil(1998), who reported a positive correlation between seed mass. Large seeds have higher amount of reserves in their cotyledons and need longer time to incorporate these nutrients in seedling tissues (Primack1987).The seeds from Dongola which had the lowest seed weight ranked second in seed germination percentage (88%). This result may be attributed to suitable environment as the seed come from hash environment and the results are in line with(Singh et al. 2010) and (Shu et al. 2012). On the other hand,(Ginwalet al. 2005) recorded that environment parameters play an important role in controlling the growth and development of plants and their effect on seed germination is quite complex because it affects each stage of germination process in a different way and is not independent of other factors. Speed of germination was recorded highest at north (25.6) and lowest at East (22.3). Similarly the mean daily germination was recorded maximum (32.4) at North and minimum (23.7) at East. Germination value was recorded maximum at North (1.9) and minimum at East (1.05) and this in line with Fandohan et al. (2010) who noted that larger seeds showed higher growth speed than smaller ones and that seed traits can be determinants for seedling growth and survival during early life stages of plants. Variation among the provenances might be attributed to genetic differences caused by the adaptation of different provenances to diverse environmental conditions and soil types, (Elmagboul et al. 2014) stated that environment parameters play an important role in controlling the growth and development of plants and their effect on seed germination is quite complex, because it affects each stage of germination process in a different way and is not independent of other factors. Amongst the various factors that determine climate, rain and temperature, are the most significant role-player affecting natural geographical plant distribution, tree performance, physiology and productivity (Shu et al. 2012).

Table 2. Effect of seeds sources on seedlings performance in the 3rd month of *Moringa oleifera* seed germination grown in four provenances

Direction	Number of leaves plant ⁻¹	Shoot length	Stem diameter	Root length	Total fresh yield	Total dry yield
			(cm)			
Eastern(Gedaref)	199.2 a	60.9 a	4.5 a	11.3 a	54.7 a	26.3 a
Northern(Dongola)	122.0 b	54.9 a	2.3 b	12.0 a	50.4 a	23.8 a
Central (Ad Diwem)	66.90 c	47.7 b	1.3 c	11.5 a	40.5 b	20.3 b
Western (Elfasher)	58.6 0c	42.1 b	1.6 c	7.8 b	23.5 c	11.3 c
P≤	0.001	0.0001	0.001	0.04	0.001	0.001
SE±	15.0	4.0	0.30	1.10	1.70	0.6 0
CV	72	38	33	48	16	16

Tables (2) showed mean seedling characteristic by four provinces for *Moringa oleifera* at 3rd month of growth. Seedling growth evaluated in assessment of six growth

parameters. Among provenances considerable variation was found in seedling height, diameter at root collar and number of leaves. Analysis of variance showed highly significant differences ($p \leq 0.0001$) in seedling height, significant differences ($p \leq 0.001$) in seedling diameter at root collar and leaves number. Variation in diameter at root collar was regionally structured since Eastern provenances (Gedaref) exhibited the highest diameter at root collar consistently the lowest at Central province (Ad Diwem). The diameter growth in the early stages could predict the diameter growth at late stages (Ibrahim, 1996; Dangasuket al. 2001). Stem diameter has been reported to be more sensitive to environmental effects than height (Lohaet al. 2006). Therefore, it is risky to use these criteria as the sole indicator for seed selection. (Takuathung et al. 2012) stated that the diameter at root collar is very sensitive to environment. Highly significant variation in leaf number per provenances was observed (Table 2). These present findings are in conformity with the observations of Singh et al. (2010) who reported significant variation in the number of leaves per plant in *Quercus glauca* and attributed to wide range of distribution of the species. Significant correlations between some geo-climatic factors and number of leaves imply that variation due to seed source origin could also have affected seedling leaf production. Correlated quantitative characters are of a major interest in an improvement program, as the improvement of one character may cause simultaneous changes in the other character (Lohaet al. 2006; Shu et al. 2012).

The results also showed significant differences in root length of the four provenances. It is apparent that root in Northern (Dongola) the fastest in growing. It may be due to it find suitable condition as it comes from harsh condition in their habitat. Another important aspect of the relation between seed and seedling weight is the resource allocation for root or shoot. In general, seedlings that originate from smaller seeds must allocate a greater proportional amount of resources to root development, resulting in lower shoot: root ratio (Yang and Midmore 2005) as observed in this study. The high investment in root tissues promotes greater development of root systems that reach deeper levels of substrate with more water and nutrients (Cana dell and Sadler (1995). Thus, this resource reallocation between root and shoot could increase the survivorship chance of seedlings with poor cotyledons reserves. The maximum shoot height and fresh yield attained also by Eastern provenances and Western is the least one in the fresh and dry yield (Table 2) and it may be due to seed weight; large seed have high energy for germination (Fenner (1978)).

Table 3. Effect of seeds sources on fresh and dry weight in the 3rd month of *Moringa oleifera* grown in the four provenances

Direction	Root fresh weight	Root dry weight	Shoot fresh weight	Shoot dry weight	Shoot: root length ratio	Shoot: root fresh weight ratio
	(g)					
Eastern (Gedaref)	17.7	8.8	35.3	17.5	3.7	2.01
Northern (Dongola)	16.4	7.9	32.7	15.9	4.3	2.05
Central (Ad Diwem)	13.5	6.8	27.1	13.5	3.5	2.007
Western (Elfasher)	7.8	3.8	15.7	7.5	4.9	2.09

The results obtained from table (3) showed moderate significant variation of fresh and dry weight at 3rd months. The Eastern provenances (Gedaref) recorded biggest root fresh and

dry weight. However, Northern (Dongola) provenances ranked in the second place and Western (Elfasher) provenances came in the lowest ranking place with a root fresh weight. Generally it has been argued that whenever the environment consists of a favorable habitat, a parent does its best by producing only small offspring, and when conditions are reversed, production of larger offspring could be advantageous (McGinley et al. 1987). Seedlings originated from larger seeds have both more time for development and nutrients available for growth. Thus, the result observed in this study agrees with the general prediction that larger seeds produce seedlings with larger initial size as reported by others authors (Leishman 2001; Yanlong et al. 2007; Fagundes et al. 2011).

Conclusion

The results showed higher growth speeds of larger seed than smaller. Seedling characteristics are variable between provenances. These variables are crucial for survival in arid and semi-arid conditions as the seedlings were sturdier and the root system can penetrate longer deep in the soil for moisture even in the drier season. The Eastern provenances showed the maximum shoot height and fresh yield and it may be due to seed weight; large seed have high energy for germination.

Recommendations

1. Caution should be made, when transfer seed from one provenance to others, because each plant is adapted to its own specific climate condition
2. Comprehensive provenances treatments are indispensable to facilitate drawing more results on its adaptive.

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